

Appendix B

How to Run the Code

This appendix provides comprehensive instructions for running the software presented in this thesis. The `optimal_stopping` software framework implements all algorithms, payoff structures, and stochastic processes described in the preceding chapters. The complete source code is available at¹:

<https://github.com/Daniel-Souza7/thesis-new-files>

B.1 Installation and Setup

B.1.1 System Requirements

The software requires the following minimum specifications:

- **Python:** Version 3.8 or higher (3.13 is recommended)
- **Memory:** 8 GB RAM minimum; 32+ GB recommended for high-dimensional runs ($d \geq 100$)
- **Storage:** 16 GB+ for pre-computed path datasets (optional)

B.1.2 Installation Procedure

1. **Clone the repository:**

```
git clone https://github.com/Daniel-Souza7/thesis-new-files.git
cd thesis-new-files
```

2. **Create a virtual environment (recommended):**

```
python -m venv venv
source venv/bin/activate # Linux/macOS
venv\Scripts\activate # Windows
```

3. **Install dependencies:**

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

4. **Verify installation:**

```
python -c "from optimal_stopping.run.run_algo import _ALGOS; \
print(f'Loaded {len(_ALGOS)} algorithms!')"
```

Expected output: Loaded 21 algorithms!

¹The repository code predates the final ARLSM naming and uses the old 'RT' acronym which stands for the Randomized Thesis algorithm. To call ARLSM, use 'RT' in your configuration.

B.2 Configuration System

The framework employs a declarative configuration system where all parameters are specified in `optimal_stopping/run/configs.py`. Each configuration is defined as a Python dataclass with parameters specified as iterables, enabling automatic grid search over all parameter combinations.

B.2.1 Default Configuration Parameters

Table B.1 summarizes all configuration parameters alongside their default values and references to thesis definitions. When building a configuration using `_DefaultConfig()` without specifying a parameter, it falls back to its default value. Parameters are grouped by category for clarity.

Table B.1 Core configuration parameters and their default values.

Parameter	Type	Symbol	Default	Ref.	Notes
<i>Algorithm Selection</i>					
<code>algos</code>	str	—	('RT', 'RLSM')	2, 3.1	Main Algorithms: RT, RLSM, LSM, DOS, NLSM
<code>hidden_size</code>	int	H	(None,)	3.1.1	None applies Equation B.1 for RT or 20 for RLSM
<code>activation</code>	str	$\phi(\cdot)$	('leakyrelu',)	C.7	Options: <code>relu</code> , <code>leakyrelu</code> , <code>elu</code> , <code>tanh</code>
<code>dropout</code>	float	—	(0.0,)	C	Regularization that kills $\in [0, 1]$ of neurons
<code>train_ITM_only</code>	bool	—	(True,)	2.2	Train only on in-the-money paths
<code>use_payoff_as_input</code>	bool	—	(True,)	3.1.2	Include $g(x)$ as network input
<code>nb_epochs</code>	int	L	(30,)	2.6, A	Training epochs (FQI/RFQI/DOS/NLSM only)
<i>Problem Specification</i>					
<code>payoffs</code>	str	$g(x)$	('BskCall',)	3.3	360 payoffs available; see library here
<code>stock_models</code>	str	—	('BlackScholes',)	3.2	BlackScholes, Heston, RealData, etc.
<code>nb_stocks</code>	int	d	(1,)	2	Number of underlying assets
<i>Market Parameters</i>					
<code>drift</code>	float	r	(0.08,)	3.2.1	Risk-free rate
<code>volatilities</code>	float	σ	(0.2,)	3.2.1	Volatility; $\sqrt{v_0}$ for Heston
<code>dividends</code>	float	q	(0.0,)	3.2.1	Continuous dividend yield
<code>correlation</code>	float	ρ	(0.0,)	3.2.2	Cross-asset or price-variance corr.
<code>spots</code>	float	S_0	(100,)	3.2	Initial spot price
<code>strikes</code>	float	K	(100,)	3.2	Strike price
<code>maturities</code>	float	T	(1,)	3.2	Time to maturity (years)
<i>Simulation Parameters</i>					
<code>nb_paths</code>	int	$m_s/2$	(8000000,)	4.1	Paths per stock per phase (train and eval)
<code>nb_dates</code>	int	N	(100,)	4.1	Number of exercisable dates equally distributed
<code>nb_runs</code>	int	—	1	4.1	Independent repetitions of train and eval
<code>dtype</code>	str	—	('float32',)	3.1.2	Precision; float32 recommended
<i>Stochastic Volatility (Heston/Rough Heston)</i>					
<code>mean</code>	float	θ	(0.3,)	3.2.2	Long-run variance level
<code>speed</code>	float	κ	(0.15,)	3.2.2	Mean reversion speed
<code>hurst</code>	float	Hu	(0.75,)	3.2.4	Hurst param; $Hu > 0.5$ is persistence
<i>Barrier Options</i>					
<code>barriers</code>	float	B	(100000,)	3.3.2	Single barrier; used for UO,DO,UI,DI, StepB and PTB
<code>barriers_up</code>	float	B_U	(100000,)	3.3.2	Upper barrier; exclusively for double barrier options
<code>barriers_down</code>	float	B_L	(1,)	3.3.2	Lower barrier; exclusively for double barrier options
<code>use_barrier_as_input</code>	bool	—	(False,)	3.1.2	Include barrier as network input (not recommended)
<i>Rank-Based Payoffs</i>					
<code>k</code>	int	k	(2,)	3.3.1	For best-of- k / worst-of- k options
<code>weights</code>	tuple	w	(None,)	3.3.1	Rank weights; ((0.3,0.7)) \rightarrow 30% 1st stock, 70% 2nd
<i>Data Sources</i>					
<code>user_data_file</code>	str	—	None	B	File in <code>user_data/</code> ; .csv

Important: When `hidden_size=None`, the RT algorithm sets the hidden-layer width using the dimension-adaptive heuristic in Equation B.1, which scales linearly with the state dimension d .

$$K(d) = \max(2d, 5) \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{1 \leq d \leq 9\}} + 1.5d \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{10 \leq d \leq 49\}} + 1.4d \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{50 \leq d \leq 99\}} + 1.3d \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{100 \leq d \leq 249\}} + 1.25d \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{250 \leq d \leq 499\}} + 1.2d \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{d \geq 500\}}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

However for max–min or other path-dependent problems, the heuristic mentioned in Section 3.1.1 that divides the number of neurons by 3 and applies ELU activation is *not* modified automatically. Any reduction in K or change in activation function (e.g. ELU/GELU) must be specified in the configuration.

B.2.2 Configuration Structure

A configuration is created by instantiating `_DefaultConfig` with the desired parameter overrides:

```
# In optimal_stopping/run/configs.py write the configurations:
my_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
    # Algorithm selection
    algos=['RT', 'RLSM', 'EOP'],

    # Problem specification (override defaults)
    payoffs=['BskCall', 'MaxCall'],
    stock_models=['BlackScholes'],
    nb_stocks=[5, 50],

    # Market parameters (override defaults)
    drift=[0.05],
    volatilities=[0.28],

    # Simulation parameters (override defaults)
    nb_paths=[100000],
    nb_dates=[100],
    nb_runs=5,

    # Algorithm hyperparameters (override defaults)
    hidden_size=[75],
    activation=['leakyrelu'],
    use_payoff_as_input=[True],
    train_ITM_only=[True],
)
```

If one tried to run the configuration above as it currently is, it would generate a total $3 \times 2 \times 2 = 12$ experimental combinations (3 algorithms \times 2 payoffs \times 2 dimensions), each repeated `nb_runs=5` times, resulting in 60 Monte Carlo training runs and 60 independent evaluation runs. For each combination, the number of simulated paths scales as `nb_paths \times nb_stocks`, yielding a total of: $6 \times 100,000 \times 5 \times 2 + 6 \times 100,000 \times 50 \times 2 = 66,000,000$ simulated paths across all experiments. Note that the computational load is highly unbalanced: the configurations with 50 stocks generate 10M paths each, whereas those with 5 stocks generate only 1M paths each. For this reason, it is recommended using separate configurations when benchmarking different values of `nb_stocks`. Hereafter, the configurations will be separated by `nb_stocks` each with `nb_paths \approx 5M/nb_stocks`

B.3 Running Experiments

B.3.1 Basic Execution

Once a configuration is defined in `configs.py`, experiments are executed via the command line:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=my_experiment
```

The results are automatically saved to `./output/metrics_draft/{timestamp}.csv`

B.3.2 Results Aggregation

To aggregate results into an Excel file with summary statistics (recommended):

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.write_excel --configs=my_experiment
```

This generates `my_experiment_summary.xlsx` containing mean prices, standard deviations, and execution times for each configuration. Only execute this after obtaining results from `run_algo`.

B.3.3 Command-Line Options

The execution script supports several options for filtering and customization:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=my_experiment \
  --nb_jobs=8 \           # Parallel CPU workers
  --algos=RT,RLSM \      # Filter algorithms
  --nb_stocks=50 \       # Filter dimensions
  --path_gen_seed=42 \   # Reproducible paths
  --print_errors         # Show full error traces
```

Multiple configurations can be run or aggregated into an Excel simultaneously, for example:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=exp1,exp2,exp3
python -m optimal_stopping.run.write_excel --configs=exp1,exp2,exp3
```

B.4 Reproducing Thesis Results

This section provides instructions to reproduce selected results from Chapter 4. The experiments require pre-computed path datasets to ensure reproducibility. These datasets are available at this drive:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1QVHAzgOZjcE3zN3rTba81LQ-GmGk5wWx>

The users can download the desired `.h5` files and place them in the `./data/stored_paths/` directory. For the framework to load these files the users must inform it by specifying in the experiment configuration `stock_models=['{Model}Stored{ID}']`, which corresponds to the file `{Model}_{ID}.h5`. This usage will be demonstrated in subsequent experiments. Alternatively, users may run experiments with freshly generated paths by setting `stock_models=['BlackScholes']` (or another process).

The dataset specifications in Table 4.1 (Section 4.1) serve as the primary reference for all configurations used throughout this thesis. For this tutorial, the focus will be on reproducing two rows from Table 4.3 and one row from Table 4.5. These experiments use datasets with `nb_dates = 20` instead of 100, requiring five times less memory and making them more likely to be handled on standard hardware.

Step 1: Download Required Datasets

Navigate to the drive and download the following three datasets: `RH_5.h5`, `SBB_25.h5`, and `BS_250.h5`. Place these files in `optimal_stopping/data/stored_paths/` before proceeding to the next step.

Step 2: Target Results and Dataset Specifications

Table B.2 specifies the eight pricing results aimed to be reproduced, with their dataset configurations. These experiments validate: (i) activation function selection (RT's ELU vs. RLSM's LeakyReLU), (ii) dimensional scalability across different process types, and (iii) barrier implementation correctness.

Table B.2 Reference prices and dataset specifications for reproduction.

Payoff	stock_model ID	d	Algorithm	Dataset Parameters	Expected Price
MaxCall	RHStored5	5	EOP	$\text{nb_paths} = 1\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20^a$	48.948
MaxCall	RHStored5	5	RT	$\text{nb_paths} = 1\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20$	48.931
MaxCall	RHStored5	5	RLSM	$\text{nb_paths} = 1\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20$	48.780
MaxCall	BSStored250	250	EOP	$\text{nb_paths} = 0.02\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20$	48.608
MaxCall	BSStored250	250	RT	$\text{nb_paths} = 0.02\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20$	48.580
MaxCall	BSStored250	250	RLSM	$\text{nb_paths} = 0.02\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = 0.2, T = 0.5, N = 20$	48.553
DO-MaxCall ^b	SBBStored25	25	EOP	$\text{nb_paths} = 0.2\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = \text{Hist.}, T = 0.5, N = 20$	45.492
DO-MaxCall ^b	SBBStored25	25	RT	$\text{nb_paths} = 0.2\text{M}, r = 0.02, \sigma = \text{Hist.}, T = 0.5, N = 20$	45.458

^aRH_5 uses Rough Heston: $\theta = 0.3, \kappa = 0.15, H = 0.75$. All datasets use `float32` precision.

^bDown-and-Out MaxCall with extreme barrier $B = 10^{-3}$ ensures convergence to European price.

Exact matches to these reference prices confirm correct configuration. Deviations exceeding 1% typically indicate setup errors (incorrect dataset, wrong algorithm parameters, or misspecified payoff). Subsequently, create separate configurations for each dimension (to adapt `nb_paths` to `nb_stocks`):

In this step one could think to write the first configuration, for the `nb_stocks = 5`, like so:

```
d5_part1_poorly_written = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RLSM', 'EOP'], payoffs=['MaxCall'], stock_models=['RHStored5'], nb_stocks
        =[5], nb_paths=[1000000], nb_dates=[20], nb_runs=1, drift=[0.02],
        volatilities=[0.2], spots=[100], strikes=[100], maturities=[0.5], hidden_size
        =[None], activation=['leakyrelu'], use_payoff_as_input=[True], dtype=['
            float32'], mean=[0.3], speed=[0.15], hurst=[0.75],
    )
```

However, this would not make use of the default parameters from B.1. To avoid this redundancy, the best way to write the configurations is to only write down the parameters that need to be overwritten:

```
d5_part1 = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RLSM', 'EOP'], payoffs=['MaxCall'], stock_models=['RHStored5'], nb_stocks
        =[5], nb_paths=[1000000], nb_dates=[20], drift=[0.02], maturities=[0.5],)
```

Having established the efficient way to write the configurations, this method will be used henceforth, omitting default parameters. The rest of the table B.2 would require the following configurations:

```

d5_part2 = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RT'], payoffs=['MaxCall'], stock_models=['
    RHStored5'], nb_stocks=5, nb_paths=100000, nb_dates=20, nb_runs=1,
    drift=[0.02], maturities=[0.5],
    activation=['elu'], # adapted to max/mins / path_dependency
    hidden_size=[4], # round(max(10, 2d)/3) See section 3.1.1.
)

d250_part1 = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RLSM', 'EOP'], stock_models=['BSStored250'],
    payoffs=['MaxCall'], nb_stocks=250, nb_paths=20000, nb_dates=20, drift
    =[0.02], maturities=[0.5])

d250_part2 = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RT'], stock_models=['BSStored250'], payoffs=[
    'MaxCall'], nb_stocks=250, nb_paths=20000, nb_dates=20, drift=[0.02],
    maturities=[0.5], hidden_size=[103], #250*1.25/3
    activation=['elu'])

d25_p1 = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RLSM', 'EOP'], stock_models=['SBBStored25'],
    payoffs=['D0-MaxCall'], nb_stocks=25, nb_paths=200000, nb_dates=20,
    drift=[0.02], maturities=[0.5], barriers=[0.001],)

d25_p2 = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RT'], stock_models=['SBBStored25'], payoffs=['D0-
    MaxCall'], nb_stocks=25, nb_paths=200000, nb_dates=20, drift=[0.02],
    maturities=[0.5], hidden_size=[15], activation=['elu'], barriers=[0.001],)

```

Execute all configurations:

```

python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=d5_part1,d5_part2,d250_part1,
    d250_part2,d25_p1,d25_p2
#After run_algo finishes executing, proceed to aggregate results:
python -m optimal_stopping.run.write_excel --configs=d5_part1,d5_part2,d250_part1
    ,d250_part2,d25_p1,d25_p2

```

The results should match the expected price of Table B.2.

Similarly, the results of other experiments are reproducible using the right configurations and datasets.

B.5 Example Configurations

This section provides ready-to-use configurations for common experimental scenarios.

B.5.1 Fresh Black-Scholes Paths

Run experiments with freshly generated GBM paths (no stored data required):

```

fresh_bs_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT', 'RLSM', 'LSM'],
    payoffs=['BskCall', 'MaxCall', 'MinPut', 'BskPut'], #Should be written with
    abbreviation from payoff dictionary

```

```

stock_models=['BlackScholes'],
nb_stocks=[5],
nb_paths=[1000000], #Recommended: nb_paths= 5M/nb_stocks
nb_runs=10, #Multiples runs to assess model stability
drift=[0.01, 0.05, 0.08], #Testing effect of drift
nb_dates=[10], #Tremendously influences speed and memory
)

```

B.5.2 Real Market Data (Stationary Block Bootstrap)

Validate algorithms using historical S&P 500 data:

```

real_data_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT'], payoffs=['GeoCall', 'GeoPut'], stock_models=['RealData'], nb_
        stocks=[50], nb_paths=[100000], #5M/50
    maturities=[0.5], #Semester
    nb_dates=[126], #Daily exercisable dates
    nb_runs=1, spots=[90, 100, 110], #Testing OTM, ATM and ITM
    drift = 0.01 #Overwrite historical drift
    volatilities = None #Allow historical vol.
)

```

The RealData model automatically downloads historical data from Yahoo Finance and applies stationary block bootstrap to generate paths. Around 250 stocks are available for nb_stocks

B.5.3 Barrier Options

Configure single and double barrier options:

```

# Single barrier (Up-and-Out, Down-and-In)
single_barrier_exp = _DefaultConfig(algos=['RT', 'RRLSM'], #RRLSM does not work
    with path-dependency
    payoffs=['UO-BskCall', 'DI-MaxCall'], #Visit dictionary
    stock_models=['BlackScholes'], nb_stocks=[30],
    nb_paths=[200000], #around 5M/30
    barriers=[120], # Single barrier level B
    hidden_size=[20], activation=['elu'], )

```

```

# Double barrier (Up-Out-Down-Out, Up-In-Down-Out)
double_barrier_exp = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT', 'RRLSM'],
    payoffs=['UODO-BasketCall', 'UIDO-MinPut'],
    stock_models=['RoughHeston'],
    nb_stocks=[100], nb_paths=[50000], hidden_size=[50], activation=['elu'],
    barriers_up=[140], # Upper barrier B_U
    barriers_down=[70], # Lower barrier B_L
    hurst=[0.3], #Rough Heston
)

```

B.5.4 Path-Dependent Options

Configure Asian and lookback options:

```
path_dependent_exp = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT', 'RRLSM'], #Use RRLSM instead of RLSM
    payoffs=[
        'LBF1-Call',
        'LBFi-Put',
        'AsianFi-Call',
        'AsianFl-Put',
    ],
    stock_models=['BlackScholes'],
    nb_stocks=[1],
    nb_paths=[5000000],
    nb_dates=[50], hidden_size=[5]
    activation=['elu'], # ELU recommended for path-dependent
)
```

B.5.5 Heston Stochastic Volatility

```
heston_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT', 'RLSM'],
    payoffs=['BskCall'],
    stock_models=['Heston'],
    nb_stocks=[70],
    nb_paths=100000
    drift=[0.05],
    volatilities=[0.18], # Initial volatility sqrt(v_0)
    mean=[0.04], # Long-run variance theta
    speed=[2.0], # Mean reversion kappa
    correlation=[-0.1],
)
```

B.5.6 Rough Heston

Note: Rough Heston path generation is computationally expensive. It is strongly recommended to use stored paths (see Section B.6.4).

```
rough_heston_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
    algos=['RT', 'RLSM'],
    payoffs=['Disp-BskCall'], #Dispersion call
    strikes=[1], #DispCall needs adjusted strike!
    stock_models=['RoughHeston'],
    nb_stocks=[5],
    hurst=[0.1], # Roughness parameter H
    mean=[0.3], # theta
    speed=[0.15], # kappa
)
```

```
correlation=[-0.1],      # rho
nb_paths=[500000],      # Reduced due to slow generation
)
```

B.6 Additional Functionalities

The framework provides several additional tools for analysis and visualization.

B.6.1 Convergence Plots

Generate plots showing how option prices converge with respect to a varying parameter:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.plot_convergence --configs=my_experiment
```

This produces publication-quality figures showing price convergence over Monte Carlo paths, 95% confidence intervals (t-distribution), and algorithm comparison across dimensions.

B.6.2 Exercise Policy Videos

Create animated visualizations of optimal exercise decisions:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.create_video \
    --config=my_experiment \
    --nb_paths_to_plot=100
```

The video shows stock price paths evolving over time, exercise decisions marked with red dots, paths grayed out after exercise, and running statistics with payoff evolution.

B.6.3 Results to Excel

Aggregate raw CSV results into formatted Excel files:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.write_excel --configs=my_experiment
```

Output file `my_experiment_summary.xlsx` contains mean prices per configuration, standard deviations and confidence intervals, execution times, and relative errors (when benchmark available).

B.6.4 Store Paths for Reproducibility

Pre-generate and store paths for exact reproducibility, particularly important for slow models like Rough Heston:

```
# Store RealData paths
python -m optimal_stopping.data.store_paths \
    --stock_model=RealData \
    --nb_stocks=50 \
    --nb_paths=100000 \
    --nb_dates=252 \
    --maturity=1.0

# Store Rough Heston paths (slow, do once)
```

```
python -m optimal_stopping.data.store_paths \
  --stock_model=RoughHeston \
  --nb_stocks=5 \
  --nb_paths=100000 \
  --nb_dates=100 \
  --maturity=1.0 \
  --hurst=0.1

# List stored paths
python -m optimal_stopping.data.store_paths --list
```

Use stored paths in configurations:

```
stored_paths_exp = _DefaultConfig(
  stock_models=['RealDataStored1732000000123'], # Use storage ID
  nb_stocks=[10], # Can use subset
  nb_paths=[50000], # Can use subset
  nb_dates=[252], # Must match exactly
  maturities=[1.0], # Must match exactly
  spots=[90, 100], # Can rescale
)
```

B.7 Hyperparameter Optimization

The framework includes Bayesian hyperparameter optimization via Optuna. Table B.3 summarizes the optimization parameters.

Table B.3 Hyperparameter optimization configuration.

Parameter	Type	Default	Description
enable_hyperopt	bool	False	Enable optimization
hyperopt_method	str	'tpe'	'tpe' or 'random'
hyperopt_timeout	float	1200	Timeout (seconds)
hyperopt_n_trials	int	None	Max trials (None = timeout)
hyperopt_fidelity_factor	int	4	Use $m/4$ paths
hyperopt_variance_penalty	float	0.1	Variance penalty λ
hyperopt_output_dir	str	'hyperopt_results'	Output directory

Configure and run hyperparameter optimization:

```
hpo_experiment = _DefaultConfig(
  algos=['RT'],
  payoffs=['BasketCall'],
  stock_models=['BlackScholes'],
  nb_stocks=[50],
  nb_paths=[1000000],
  # Enable hyperparameter optimization
  enable_hyperopt=True,
  hyperopt_method='tpe', # Bayesian optimization
```

```

hyperopt_timeout=3600,      # 1 hour
hyperopt_n_trials=100,
hyperopt_fidelity_factor=4, # Use 1/4 of paths
hyperopt_variance_penalty=0.1,
)

```

Execute optimization:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_hyperopt --configs=hpo_experiment
```

B.8 Troubleshooting

B.8.1 Memory Issues

For high-dimensional problems ($d \geq 100$) or large path counts ($m \geq 10^7$):

```

memory_efficient_exp = _DefaultConfig(
    dtype=['float32'],      # Use single precision
    nb_paths=[1000000],    # Reduce path count
    nb_dates=[10],        # Reduce exercisable dates
    nb_stocks=[50],       # Reduce the dimension
)

```

Reduce parallelism:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=exp --nb_jobs=4
```

B.8.2 Algorithm Not Found

Algorithm names are case-sensitive:

```

algos=['RT', 'RLSM', 'LSM'] # Correct
algos=['rt', 'rlsm', 'lsm'] # Incorrect

```

Find the entire abbreviation list for all algorithms in the `run_algo.py` file. Search for `_ALGOS`.

B.8.3 Reproducibility

For exact reproducibility across runs use `path_gen_seed`:

```
python -m optimal_stopping.run.run_algo --configs=exp --path_gen_seed=42
```

B.9 Summary

The `optimal_stopping` framework provides complete infrastructure for American option pricing research. The typical workflow involves defining a configuration via `_DefaultConfig(...)` in the `configs.py` file, executing with `run_algo`, aggregating and interpreting results with `write_excel`.

For additional guidance, the GitHub repository contains folder-specific README files with detailed instructions and context for each module. For questions or issues, users may open an issue on GitHub or contact the author directly through `daniel.souza.tyui@gmail.com`.